

QUIZ**LAST NAME: EDJETA JOBIR****FIRST NAME: BULI****PROGRAM CODE : DSDD****COURSE CODE : DSDD****PERIOD NUMBER: ACA-401D****INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes).

The author did not use Zotero to insert references.

The author used the following software: MSOffice 2011, Mac

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

1. **One of the following does not make a good choice of a research topic.**

- A research topic should be as broad as possible.¹**
- A research topic should be one that interests you.
- A researchable topic should be manageable as much as possible
- A research topic that sparks a debate makes a good choice.

2. **One of the following is correct about sources of your research.**

- You should evaluate the relevance and reliability of your sources.²**
- Spending your time on the evaluation of your sources does not help.
- One can use primary sources only for a research work such as a thesis

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis and Dissertations*: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2013), 19.

² Turabian, 28.

- For PhD research work, you can limit your sources to the materials covered by the course only.
3. **As noted elsewhere, a researcher should build his/her writings with his/her own ideas and words. But his/her thought should be supported at least by one of the following methods of using others works.**
- Quotes, paraphrase, and summaries.**³
- Hearsays.
- A speech of a prominent leader without fully making a citation of sources.
- A poet's script without reference to the sources.
4. **One of the following reasons properly describes why we cite a source.**
- To give credit to the authors; to show the correctness of your facts; to unveil the research tradition you follow; to enhance the reliability of your reasons, arguments, and conclusions.**⁴
- To show that you read as many books as possible.
- To show that you read the most famous books.
- Citing books gives pleasure.
5. **Citation, according to Turabian (2013), should contain basic information that properly identify a source. Which of the followings describes the best information one needs to offer while citing a source?**

³ Turabian, 49.

⁴ Turabian, 86.

- Editor, writer, translator (the who question); title and subtitle (what is the identity of the source?); publisher (who published it); location of the source (where to find).**⁵
- The color of the book quoted.
- The total pages of the book.
- The font and styles of the published books.
6. **The best description of the parenthetical citation and reference with regards to a single author is:**
- Use the last name of the author in both parenthetical citation and entry of reference list.**⁶
- Use the last name of the author in parenthetical citation and first name in the reference list.
- Use the last name of the author in the reference list and first name of the author in the parenthetical citation.
- Use of last and first names in both parenthetical and reference list is optional.
7. **Which of the following best describes citation and referencing of journal articles?**
- In parenthetical citation invert the names of the author, and in reference list, invert the name of the first-listed author.**⁷
- Journals are referenced just in the same way as magazines.

⁵ Turabian, 87.

⁶ Turabian, 136.

⁷ Turabian, 144.

- Journals that are accessed online can be referenced just like a book; no need to add date accessed.
 - Journals and magazines are the same.
8. **Interview and personal communication can be used in research works as data sources. Which one of the following summarizes items that we need to include in referencing interviews and personal communications?**
- Start the entry with name of the person who is interviewed; followed by the date and name of the interviewer; place and specific day of the interview; the location of transcripts or tapes.⁸**
 - Start with the name of the interviewer, followed by the name of interviewee; place and specific day of the interview; the location of transcripts or tapes.
 - Date of interview and the name of the interviewer suffices.
 - You may omit referencing interview and personal communication.
9. **Qualitative Research encompasses different kinds of traditions. Which one of the following traditions aims to ‘investigate the meanings of the *lived experience* of people to identify the core essence of human experience as described by research participants’?**
- Phenomenology.⁹**
 - Ethnography.
 - Hermeneutics.
 - Grounded Theory.

⁸ Turabian, 150.

⁹ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (California: Sage Publications, 2008), 11.

10. **What is the standard English used in the European Commission authors and translators guide and recommended for European English Usage?**

- British English.**¹⁰
- American English.
- Mix of American and British English.
- Other European language, such as French.

¹⁰ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 8th edition (European Commission, 2016), 7.
https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/info/files/styleguide_english_dgt_en.pdf

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